

**PHILOSOPHICAL IDEAS OF DEATH AND IMMORTALITY IN THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF
P. NESTERENKO**

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Abstract

The article is the first to explore the philosophical ideas of death and immortality in the scientific heritage of the Ukrainian philosopher and psychologist Pavel Aleksandrovich Nesterenko (Lyubomir Bogoyavlensky).

Among the key philosophical ideas about death and immortality of P. Nesterenko, the author singles out: 1. Humanity has a desire for the immortality of Osiris. 2. P. Nesterenko for the first time investigated the concept of death and immortality in currents of world Satanism. 3. P. Nesterenko proved the philosophical correlation between ideas about death and immortality and a person's worldview.

Keywords: death, immortality, personality, P. Nesterenko, gay, LGBT, the philosopher, the scientist, Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky, the Genius.

Introduction. According to the Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary, philosophy is “a form of social consciousness; the doctrine of the general principles of being and knowledge, of man’s relationship to the world; the science of the universal laws of development of nature, society and thinking” [2, c. 726].

Philosophers create philosophy. The Russian-Ukrainian war affected the development of all key spheres of Ukrainian society: scientific, cultural, philosophical, religious, and others.

Ukrainian philosophy faced an important task – to single out the names of living Ukrainian philosophers who are the creators of modern Ukrainian science and philosophy.

One of the creators of modern Ukrainian philosophical anthropology is the Ukrainian philosopher, psychologist and esotericist P. Nesterenko (Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky).

Philosophical heritage of P. Nesterenko is contained in his two candidate theses (philosophy and psychology), in scientific articles and philosophical books.

The main motives of P. Nesterenko's scientific and philosophical work are the problem of death and immortality. The main philosophical works on this issue in the creative heritage of P. Nesterenko can be singled out:

1. “Teachings of Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky” (2016) [5].
2. “The Mystical Path of the Gay or Tarot of the Devil by Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky” (2018) [1].
3. “The desire for immortality of Osiris in the human being” (2021) [6].
4. “The problem of death and immortality in destructive neo-religions” (2021) [3].
5. “Perceptions of the death and immortality of the individual in everyday, personal and philosophical types of worldview” (2022) [4].

The aim of the article is to analyze the philosophical ideas of death and immortality in the scientific heritage of the Ukrainian philosopher and psychologist Pavlo Nesterenko (Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky).

Results. Let's begin our research with a short biographical reference about the scientist. Pavlo Oleksandrovych Nesterenko (creative pseudonym Lubomyr

Bogoyavlensky) was born on July 9, 1987 in Bobrovytsia, Chernihiv region, Ukraine.

It is known from open sources that P. Nesterenko is a person with special mental activity, he has been diagnosed with schizotypal disorder since the age of twelve and throughout his life. He underwent diagnosis and treatment at the Kyiv mental hospital “Clinical Hospital of Psychiatry” (an analogy with F. Nietzsche emerges).

Pavlo Nesterenko has also been openly gay and a fighter for gay rights in Ukraine all his life. Despite the terrible persecution at school for his open homosexuality, at the age of 18, the young philosopher enrolled to study psychology for 6 years at the full-time department at Nizhyn Mykola Gogol State University (Nizhyn city, Ukraine) [1].

Sharing his memories of years of persecution, the thinker P. Nesterenko writes: “To understand Gay, you need to live as a gay man in our homophobic society and experience first-hand the despair and horror of homophobia, misunderstanding, contempt, persecution and disaster that most homosexual men experience. It’s especially tragic for a gay man if, like me, he comes from the bottom of society, from a very poor family... And if you are also a gentle, feminine, sensitive and vulnerable gay man, then your adaptation and ability to survive in society will be significantly disrupted and you will have to survive even harder.

... In my 30 years of personal experience, as an openly gay man, I have gone through such a hell of homophobia and persecution that most people in my place would go crazy or commit suicide. But I didn’t break down, I never made a single suicide attempt, I never drank and don’t drink alcohol, I don’t smoke, and I’ve never taken drugs even once. I hardened myself and became a Strong Spirit” [1, c. 30–31].

We are convinced that precisely in connection with the schizotypal disorder and the many years of persecution he experienced for being gay, the problem of death and immortality of the individual is acutely present in the scientific and artistic work of the poet, psychologist and philosopher P. Nesterenko.

After six years of training as a psychologist at Nizhyn Mykola Gogol State University, P. Nesterenko

became a certified master of practical psychology and a practical psychologist. And in 2015, P. Nesterenko obtained a second higher education – a teacher of English language and foreign literature (he graduated from National Pedagogical Drahomanov University, Kyiv, Ukraine) [1].

Based on the study of the biography and philosophical works of the scientist Pavlo Nesterenko, we can come to the conclusion that he is a unique Ukrainian philosopher and psychologist who very subtly understands the nature of the human soul.

After many years of thinking about metaphysical phenomena, God, Satan, good, evil, light, darkness, as well as the phenomena of death and immortality, in 2016 P. Nesterenko wrote his fundamental philosophical work “Teachings of Lubomir Bogoyavlensky”.

According to P. Nesterenko, death is “an Eternal Sleep. And our earthly sleep is a connection with death. When we sleep, we come into contact with the reality of death, with the Underworld!

Why is a person afraid to die? Because he is afraid of the Laws of Eternal Sleep. That is, the Laws of Death, when you can never wake up. And this even gives some people a horror of death, because the dying person does not know what he will dream about forever. As long as a person is in the body, even if he dreams of a terrible horror, he can always wake up, return to the earthly world and forget the nightmare. And in Eternal Sleep (death), you no longer control yourself, and you cannot wake up” [5].

Therefore, for the philosopher P. Nesterenko, death is primarily a metaphysical problem that requires the involvement of the “Higher Powers” category for its explanation.

In 2018, P. Nesterenko wrote his fundamental, unique philosophical work “The Mystical Way of Gay or the Tarot of the Devil of Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky”, in which he considered the fundamental problems of human existence, and also highlighted the problem of death and immortality of personality.

In the review of this work, researcher V. Nikitenko notes that:

“1. The psychological system “The Mystical Path of Gay or the Tarot of the Devil by Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky” is psychoanalysis. A modern new psychoanalytic technique for working with the client’s unconscious.

2. I foresee that just as in the beginning, historically, society rejected and did not accept Sigmund Freud and his psychoanalysis, citing the fact that it was “unscientific and immoral,” also a large part of current society may reject the projective technique of Gay Tarot scientist-psychologist Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky. Which is due to the neuroticism of our society and the defense mechanisms of the Super-Ego. But future generations of humanity and the scientific community will appreciate this psychoanalytic system” [7, c. 18].

P. Nesterenko believes that the key to the immortality of the individual lies in the neo-pagan beliefs of our ancestors. Neopaganism itself is the way to immortality. Death as a religious embodiment of the goddess is a unique force from which a living person can draw wisdom and strength. P. Nesterenko develops the cult

of the Mexican goddess Santa Muerte in his philosophy [1].

Reflecting on the phenomenon of death, the Ukrainian poet and philosopher P. Nesterenko writes:

“When the body dies, completing its Path,
The soul will go to the Kingdom of the Father.

Santa Muerte is Holy Death,

She will send you to the Kingdom of the Dead.

You will go through the ordeal – the dungeons of the eclipse...

And you will see steps into the bosom of Love.

After all, death is only an illusion on the Path of Redemption!

After death will be Dawn and Eternity, Life!

Souls soar there! There is God's Freedom!

Freedom of Love! Freedom of Good!

There is the Imperishable Kingdom of Adam's race!

There is the reality of the Almighty,
where there is no evil!

In Radiant Paradise is Infinite Life!

Beyond Death's sunset is Eternal Dawn!

In the Kingdom of Heaven – Eternal Truth!

Don't be afraid of Death! NO DEATH!” [1, c. 106].

So, on the one hand, P. Nesterenko has a religious and mystical worldview. He personifies death as a person. On the other hand, P. Nesterenko proclaims hope for possible immortality and says that in fact death does not exist (this was also said by many religious preachers and occultists of the past).

At the beginning of 2020, P. Nesterenko begins to study postgraduate studies in philosophy at the full-time department at Mykhailo Dragomanov Ukrainian State University, and also simultaneously enrolls in postgraduate studies in psychology at Nizhyn Mykola Gogol State University.

The topic of the dissertation on philosophy, written by researcher P. Nesterenko, is called “The problem of death and immortality of personality: worldview and socio-cultural aspects.” The scientific supervisor of P. Nesterenko is a corresponding member of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Professor Nazip Vilenovich Khamitov.

Among the points of scientific novelty that P. Nesterenko published in his scientific articles, we can highlight: 1. Humanity has a desire for the immortality of Osiris [6]. 2. P. Nesterenko for the first time investigated the concept of death and immortality in currents of world Satanism [3]. 3. P. Nesterenko proved the philosophical correlation between ideas about death and immortality and a person's worldview [4].

Conclusions. So, we come to the conclusion that Pavlo Nesterenko is an “unrecognized genius”, that is, a great Ukrainian philosopher, poet and psychologist, whom the world has not yet heard of in Europe, the USA and other countries. But we are convinced that in the future everything will change and scientists from different countries of the world will still write about P. Nesterenko, and philosophers and journalists will study his biography.

P. Nesterenko's philosophical ideas about the phenomena of death and immortality are unique and require further research and philosophical analysis. We are convinced that Lubomyr Bogoyavlensky is a genius, and his philosophical discoveries will help save humanity from suicidal wars, hatred, and lack of tolerance and kindness.

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